

THE EXCELLENT EXAMPLE OF UZBEK CLASSICAL MUSIC ART - KOMILJON OTANIYOZOV

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Abstract: This article presents thoughts and opinions about the difficult creative path and sharp turns in the life of Komiljon Otaniyozov, one of the famous creators of the 20th century, a singer, musician, actor, a mature artist of his time. In addition, today's efforts to preserve the name of this artist will be carefully considered.

Key words: singer, actor, painting, status paths, epic songs, musical drama, film concert.

Introduction.

Komiljon Otaniyozov, a mature and outstanding artist of the 20th century, singer and skilled actor, was born on July 20, 1917 in the village of Boyrachi, Shavat district. In addition to being a skilled performer of Tor sozi, he is also the author of several works, a composer, a People's Artist of Uzbekistan (USSR), Turkmenistan, and Karakalpakstan. Finally, he has an attractive and powerful voice, and he has achieved artistic maturity in the interpretation of each piece.

Otaniyozov began to sing complex folk songs and songs from epics in the 1930s. Khorezm suvora and statuses were the high stage of Komiljon Otaniyozov's performance. Komiljon Otaniyozov stood out from the rest with his innovation. That is, Khorezm created a new style based on epic songs (names). As a composer, his songs such as "Hello, to you from Khorezm", "Mubarak", "Vatan", "Olqish", "Temiryol", "Uzbekistan", "Khorazm" are popular and popular. is distinguished by

In cooperation with O.A. Stepanov, he created musical dramas such as "Aziz and Sanam", "Ashiq Garib", "The Last Khan" with S. Hayitboyev. It can be seen from this that Otaniyozov was not only limited to singing and playing music, he was able to show the way of creativity by creating effective and meaningful works. This talented artist went on many tours and contributed to the wide promotion of the Khorezm performing arts school.

The main reason why he received the nickname "Nightingale of Khorezm" in his time was the fact that the main part of his work and the main performance directly promoted the Khorezm School of Performing Arts.

Komiljon Otaniyozov in one of his poems:

*"O'ylasang o'z baxtingni, el baxti birlan yor et,
Ey, Komil, nomingni sen yaxshilar ichra bor et"*

- wrote and turned this wisdom into his life belief. He was a great artist who could be an example to everyone not only with his music and voice, but also with his beautiful human qualities. It is not for nothing that his dedication to art, honesty and sincerity, kindness to people are still legends in languages.

Kamiljon Otaniyozov, who considered serving the people through art as the meaning of his life and his entire being, raised the art of classical music to a new, high level during his

short life. He glorified the Uzbek culture and the Uzbek name to the whole world with his unique, divine and magical voice.

His film concert is a wonderful work that shows the real personality and creativity of Komiljon Otaniyozov. Apart from this film, there is no other image of him acting on the screens. Therefore, this work has become a treasure of our spiritual heritage as a unique and rare picture. This "Film concert" program was distinguished from other works by its presentation. The interest of speech processes and the development of the topic directly attracted the attention of the listener.

It is noted that another unforgettable service of this great man is that he gave his heart, love and generosity and brought dozens of talented students to maturity. Today, many hafiz and artists, who have gained fame not only in Uzbekistan, but also in neighboring countries, consider him as their spiritual teacher. It is noted that Komiljon Otaniyozov, who sang the beauty of the Motherland, high human feelings such as love, love and loyalty to the Motherland, kindness, kindness, created a unique creative school as a hafiz, musician, and composer, and will remain in history. The fact that the songs created by him have taken a deep place in the hearts of millions of people and have become examples of folk art shows what a rare talent this great artist has.

Today, in the land of Khorezm, where the master artist was born and grew up, his home museum was established, the cultural and recreational park named after Komiljon Otaniyozov was reconstructed and improved in all respects in Shavot district, and a garden and creative center named after Hafiz was established in Urganch district it is worth noting that a monument with his blessed face was erected, and a beautiful statue was placed in the "Artists' Park" of Margilan city. It should also be noted that the 100th anniversary event of Komiljon Otaniyozov was widely celebrated throughout Uzbekistan by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev.

The Minister of Foreign Culture and Tourism and the Minister of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan personally participated in the ceremony together with the President. Everyone was delighted to see the young and talented personnel who participated in this event, and various proposals were made for the further reform of such events. It can be seen from this that the effective work of Khorezm nightingale has managed to attract not only 20th century musicians, but also contemporary artists from 7 to 70 years of age. In order to further preserve the name of the artist, neighborhoods and streets located in the regions were named after Komiljon Otaniyozov, and his works were included in the list of repertoires that must be performed.

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